

WORK OF COOPERATION WITH FAMILY, NEIGHBORHOOD AND SCHOOL IN PROVIDING PROFESSIONAL ASSISTANCE TO THE DEVELOPMENT AND UPBRINGING OF A CHILD IN A PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATION

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Annotation. In turn, it is necessary for the preschool organization to establish cooperation with parents. The content of the work carried out with parents is colorful, and in the process of such upbringing, it is people who combine labor and social activities with family tasks, are interested in the life of their children and are guided by them fairly, parents are positive role models. The Professional educator organizes observations, showing that the role of both family and society in the upbringing of a child's personality in cooperation with the family and Mahalla is extremely large.

Keywords: professionalism, professional educator, methods of socialization, field of education and upbringing, scientific justification of cooperation.

Special importance in the upbringing of the younger generation as well-behaved, faithful to the symbols of the state is attached to their young personality, character, because without these, the intended goal in upbringing cannot be achieved. With the cooperation of the family, neighborhood, preschool organization, the effectiveness is even higher when following the following tamails and stages.

- Cooperation process in the field of education and training workaholics work unit of action;
- harmony of respect and demand for the educator;
- the process of cooperation is equal and high responsibility of the subjects;
- priority of nation and state maanfats in the process of activity;
- scientific justification of cooperation.

The purpose of the preschool organization is to conduct an educational process that significantly implements the rights, obligations and responsibilities of the parties that arise in the process of teaching, raising, looking after and caring for children. The preschool organization provides the necessary

conditions in accordance with the Charter of preschool education. Always takes care of protecting children's lives and strengthening their health.

In the early stages of preschool age, children will have imagination education. With the increase in life experience and the development of thinking, creative imagination is formed. For children of a small preschool age, visual - moving, visual-figurative thinking is characteristic. On the basis of this, the word, logical thinking, conceptual thinking are developed. A Professional educator should be able to structure the activity of thinking in children, to deeply understand these phenomena, events, to teach them to distinguish between their important and non-essential aspects.

Just let the professionals reach the heights in their field, don't get in the way and criticize unnecessarily for doing their job skillfully!

The Professional educator, organizing observations, tries to answer the questions that arise in children in a timely manner, allowing them to search for an independent answer and not allowing curiosity to subside in children of preschool age. The children are raised in turn.

In turn, it is necessary for the preschool organization to establish cooperation with parents. This is one of the most effective ways to cooperate with the family in raising a child. The content of the work carried out with parents is colorful, in which it is necessary to discuss some issues together. For example:

- about the role of the family in raising children, about the laws on the duties of parents, about the preparation of children for school;
- on the annual Work Plan of the preschool organization;
- these are the issues about the work of the parental community.

Work forms such as group and general meetings of parents, consultations, conferences, parent nights are included in team work forms to discuss these issues collectively. A Professional educator is closely associated with family upbringing in the formation of child education.

In fact, the upbringing of a child is the responsibility of the parent to the civil duty and the state before society, and to the relatives. That is why parental authority is a spiritual fodder in the upbringing of children. This spiritual nourishment is a solid foundation in the pursuit of the "horizon" in the upbringing of a child. In the process of such upbringing, parents who combine labor and social activities with family tasks, are interested in the life of their children and are guided by them fairly, are those who become positive role models, that is, respected parents.

Such people will be intelligent people, members of exemplary families, who will pay attention to the upbringing of their children both in the family and in the Mahalla, and in preschool education.

The educator in the neighborhood should be a person under the age of 30, physically strong, with no less than 5 years of pedagogical experience, who has a good understanding of sports and business, who follows young people in the neighborhood or children with difficult upbringing, minors, and deals with them. In the implementation of these works, it is important to organize cooperation between the "neighborhood" foundations, the "maturation" social movement of young people, sports committees. Hence, the role of the family and neighborhood, a small homeland, in the upbringing of the future generation, is incomparable, due to the saying "seven neighborhoods per child-a parent".

There is a neighborhood in the city of Tashkent from the XIX century. Their organization and functioning are associated, on the one hand, with their national - psychological characteristics, and on the other hand, with the creation of an opportunity for the population to plunge into social relations from an early age. In other words, a neighborhood is a microdistrict in which methods of socialization of an individual in an even larger community are formed by following moral principles and rules, participating in rituals and other types of public activity.

Socialization not only provides for the individual to have comforts in society, but also provides for the individual to acquire certain moral and ethnic rules. In this respect, neighborhood socialization is a unique mechanism. Because in it:

- each person makes certain moral laws that must be followed;
- treatment is based on a number of moral principles;
- trust and service to authority, personal role model strength, respect for adults, care about children;
- ethics and public education are carried out through inclusion in practical activities;
- the values of public consciousness are extended from the neighborhood to the family and the individual;
- the main stages of the life of an individual are observed by all members of the team.

At the stage of preparing children for school, preschool education organization and parent interaction - preschool education organization "first step" is one of the important directions of the state curriculum. In most parents,

there is a misconception that the readiness of a child for school results in the fact that his reading, writing and counting skills are formed, his memory is good. The concept of "preparation for school" is a complex, long-term and systematic kindergarten and the process of pre-school preparation of a child in a family setting.

School readiness includes the formation of the acquisition of skills related to educational activities: compliance of the child with the system of rules when performing work, listening to adults and following their instructions, working according to the pattern, etc. It is these aspects of school preparation that will be unfamiliar to many parents.

Parents should know that preschool education is the basis of the development of a child, the formation of his culture as a person. A school is not a training place for future adults, but a place to work with others and acquire the necessary knowledge, teaching them to live in the world that surrounds the child. Most parents are not ready to consciously and responsibly approach the preparation of the child for school, the formation of a positive attitude towards acquiring knowledge, which, in turn, is the reason for the difficulties in adapting the child to school and the inability to master knowledge well.

The reasons why the child is not ready for school are manifested in the following::

- the child cannot concentrate, quickly become distracted, join the general mode of work of the group;
- his speech and mental abilities will be weakly developed, he does not know how to ask questions, compare objects, distinguish the main one;
- shows little initiative, seeks action and conclusions depending on the sample, has problems in interaction with adults and comrades.

One of the most important tasks facing the preschool organization is to teach parents to apply and co-ordinate their child in the child's preparation for school. In its content, the tips carried out by the educators of the preschool educational organization should preserve the child's ability to increase the visual abilities of the world, model in the process of cognition, productivity of imagination, sensitivity to many pedagogical influences (stability), compassion, perseverance.

The topics of parent gatherings and counseling are diverse, providing them with pedagogical and psychological support, such as "the impact of games in the formation of communicative readiness of a child in school", "What Should parents of first graders know?", "Intellectual readiness of the child for school"

education", " how to support personal pride and self – esteem in the child?", "Family games on various knowledge topics".

Thus, the role of the external social environment and upbringing in the psychic development of a person and the content of his personal qualities is decisive. This in turn indicates that the role of both family and society in the upbringing of the child's personality is extremely large.

In conclusion, in the upbringing of a child, preschool education, family and society are equally different. Because when a child receives education for the first time in the family, he further forms it in preschool education, strengthens it and acquires the elements of upbringing through a short explanation, exhortation or games.

References:

1. Рузиматов, Р. Я., Махкамов, Г. М., Отажонова, С. Р., & Турсунова, Ш. А. (2017). Промышленное развитие в Коканде, причины экологических проблем (1956-1975гг.). Высшая школа, (6), 77-78.
2. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.
3. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. (2021). Pedagogical factors of preparation of future teachers of biology for professional-pedagogical activities. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(6), 48-51.
4. Otajonova, S. (2021, July). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND. In Конференции.
5. Otajonova, S. (2021). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1318>. In RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES (No. 18.06).
6. Асқарова, М. А., Отажонова, С. Р., Алимова, М. Б., & Ирматова, М. Д. (2020). READING-INTELLIGENCE AS A CAPACITY-BUILDING TOOL. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(7), 398-402.
7. Rakhimova, G., Narimonova, Z., Otajonova, S., & Abdulxaeva, M. (2019). Stereotypy and poetics of the endemic of recit. Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems, 11(7), 966-969.
8. Norquzieva, D. S., & Abdullaeva, N. R. (2019). PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENCE. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(6), 490-495.

9. Khamidovna, M. I., Sheralievna, N. D., & Okhunovna, M. D. (2022). CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND TYPES OF CONFLICTS AMONG MINORS. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(7).
10. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 1212-1216.
11. Sheralievna, N. D. (2021). DYNAMICS OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR FORMATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(10), 666-669.
12. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 1212-1216.
13. Norqo'Ziyeva, D. S. (2021). ILK O'SPIRINLARNI KASBGA YO'NALTIRISHNING AYRIM PSIXOLOGIK MASALALARI. *Scientific progress*, 1(6), 1188-1192.
14. Бойтемирова, З., & Орипов, Э. (2016). РОЛЬ ДЕМОКРАТИЧЕСКИХ ИНСТИТУТОВ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ НАСЛЕДОВАНИЯ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In *СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ СИСТЕМАХ* (pp. 30-32).
15. Boytemirova, Z. (2020). Youth and Spiritual Security. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 181-183.
16. Aminova, M. M. (2021). The value of "5 initiatives" in the spiritual and moral education of students of secondary school. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(6), 38-42.
17. Mutalibovna, A. M. The Impact of Globalization on National Culture and Its Protection Problems. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 210-212.
18. Mutalibovna, A. M. The Modern Importance of Studying the Scientific Heritage of Ibn Khaldun. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 229-232.
19. Аминова, М. М. (2020). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ВОСПИТАНИИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ. *Интернаука*, (22-2), 51-52.
20. Mutalibovna, A. M. INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO MODERN YOUTH EDUCATION.

21. Shamsiddinov, B. J., & Jakbaraliyva, Z. (2022). Scientific and Empirical Relations of Philosophy and Literature. Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity, 7, 70-73.
22. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж., & Жакбаралиева, З. О. (2022). АБУ АЛИ ИБН СИНО ТИББИЙ ТАРБИЯ ХУСУСИДА. Oriental Art and Culture, 3(2), 670-674.
23. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж., & Алиев, А. А. Ў. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА КЎППАРТИЯВИЙЛИК ТИЗИМИ ВА ХУСУСИЙ ТАДБИРКОРЛИК. Oriental Art and Culture, 3(2), 675-682.
24. Jakbrovich, S. B. (2021, July). THE RELATIONS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP WITH SELF-GOVERNMENT INSTITUTIONS. In Euro-Asia Conferences (pp. 64-69).
25. Jakbarovich, S. B. (2021, July). DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A SOCIO-ECONOMIC BASIS OF CIVIL SOCIETY. In Euro-Asia Conferences (pp. 69-72).
26. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ МАЪНАВИЙ ҲАЁТИДА ТАДБИРКОР ВА ИШБИЛАРМОНЛАР ИШТИРОКИНИНГ ЎРНИ ВА УНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАЛҚИНИ. Oriental Art and Culture, 2(4), 565-574.
27. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж. (2021). ХУСУСИЙ ТАДБИРКОР ВА ИШБИЛАРМОНЛАР ФАОЛИЯТИНИНГ ОИЛА ВА МАҲАЛЛА ФАРОВОНЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ. Oriental Art and Culture, 2(4), 452-456.
28. Бойкузиева, Г. (2020). ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ЖЕНЩИН В СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ ЖИЗНИ ОБЩЕСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ (pp. 27-31).
29. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2017). Тарих фалсафий тадқиқот предмети сифатида. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 26-27.
30. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2017). Бағрикенглик ижтимоий-фалсафий қадрият. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 27-28.
31. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2016). Теоретическая подготовка студентов к социологическим исследованиям в практической и самостоятельной работе. In Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее (pp. 318-319).
32. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2016). Некоторые аспекты проблемных концепций осмысления динамики научного знания. In Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее (pp. 245-247).
33. МИРАХМЕДОВ, Ж. М., & БАБАЕВА, Н. М. (2016). К ВОПРОСУ О СУЩНОСТИ СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. In Будущее науки-2016 (pp. 16-19).

34. Muhsinovich, M. J. (2020). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF SPIRITUAL SAFETY AND HISTORICAL CONSCIOUSNESS. *European science review*, (9-10), 39-41.
35. Mirakhmedov, J. M. (2020). SOCIAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF NATIONAL AND SPIRITUAL SECURITY. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(8), 171-174.
36. Muhsinovich, M. J. (2020). FEATURES OF MANIFESTATION OF HISTORICAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL SECURITY. *Евразийский Союз Ученых*, (4-9 (73)), 65-66.
37. Мирахмедов, Д. М. ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ ПОДХОД ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО РАЗУМА.
38. Aminjonovna, S. O. (2021). The Importance of The Spiritual Heritage of Uzbek Enlighteners in the Education of Youth.
39. Орипов, Э. Ш., & Худойберганов, Ш. Ш. (2020). ВИРТУАЛЬНЫЙ МИР: СОДЕРЖАНИЕ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In *ВОПРОСЫ НАУКИ 2020: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ* (pp. 53-60).
40. Худойберганов, Ш. Ш., & Орипов, Э. Ш. (2020). ШОТЛАНД ОЛИМИ УИЛЬЯМ ЭРСКИН НИГОҲИДА БОБУР ТИМСОЛИ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 187-190).
41. Oripov, E. S. (2021). HISTORICAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL ROOTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRADITIONAL VALUES. *Journal of Central Asian Social Studies*, 2(01), 122-127.
42. Орипов, Э. Ш., & Абдурахмонов, З. М. (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ НОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In *ВОПРОСЫ НАУКИ 2020: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ* (pp. 61-68).
43. Shavkatovich, O. E. (2022). MILLIY G'OYA VA AN'ANAVIY QADRIYATLARGA DIALEKTIV YONDOSHUV. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(1), 261-265.
44. Abdurahmonovich, A. H. (2021). THE ISSUE OF INTERPRETING THE WORLD (BEING) NATURE ON THE THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF NATIONAL EDUCATION OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(07), 140-143.
45. Abdurahmonovich, A. H. (2022). A METHODOICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACH TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING 7TH GRADE EDUCATION IN A GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(12), 187-188.

46. Ортиқов, О. И. (2020). ИЖТИМОЙЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ МЕРОСДА МИЛЛИЙЛИК МАСАЛАСИ. Интернаука, (10-3), 63-65.
47. Urinboyev, D. (2019). Thoughts About Stratagema Of Western And Eastern Thinkers. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(4), 147-151.
48. Bakhtiyorovich, U. D. (2022). Features of the manifestation of strategems and the relationship between them. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 96-100.

